

Ethovision: Open Field Test

- Click New → create a file name → then OK
- Go to Experiment Settings
 - Number of subjects: 1
 - Tracked Features: center-point detection

Arena Settings

- Go to Arena Settings 1 → Arena Settings 1 → then click Browse
- Open the video and click Grab
 - Double-check the bin wasn't moved during the video, then return to video start with ID card/ruler
- Select 1. Draw Scale to Calibrate → draw length of ruler → type 25 (cm) → OK
- Select 2. Shape and Draw Arena → select Create Closed Polyline button on top bar
 - Click on each corner of the arena at the top of the bin walls, and double-click final/4th corner
 - Make sure the arena covers the walls and do ***NOT*** let the arena touch areas outside of the bin
- Select Zone Group 1, click the “add subdivided rectangle” button, outline the bottom of the chamber
 - 3 rows by 3 columns → OK
 - From the menu on the right, right-click and delete S1 → S9 **except S5**

- Click 4. Validate setup → OK
- Rename Arena Settings 1 to the animal ID number

Trial Control Settings

- Go to Trial Control Settings 1
 - Select, right-click, and delete first Condition box → check box next to Time
 - In the time condition box → change condition name to “Start” → select After and enter the number of seconds when the mouse first appears in the video and the experimenter is also out of view
 - Make sure there are 20 minutes of video after the mouse's start time
 - Connect all boxes in timeline with arrows; the “Start” time condition box should be in the second position
 - In the second time condition box → Settings → change condition name to “Stop” → set to stop after 20 minutes
 - Rename Trial Control Settings 1 to animal ID#

Detection Settings

- Click Detection Settings (1) → Detection Settings 1
- On the right, if necessary, click Select Video → choose the video corresponding to that trial
- On the right, click Advanced
 - Select Gray Scaling from the dropdown menu → set the range from 0-45 → select Rodents/For Occlusions from the next dropdown
 - If videos were not recorded in low lighting, see full version of NOR protocol for range details
 - Smoothing → use default settings
 - Subject contour: check the Contour Erosion box and select 3 pixels, check Contour Dilation and select 4 pixels, make sure the dropdown says Erode first, then dilate
 - Subject size minimum/maximum:
 - For 10 fps videos: use 200 min – 5000 max; for 25 fps videos: use 3,000 min - 18,000 max
 - Click Edit enter min/max numbers → Close (make sure they both registered) → Save
- On the left, right-click Detection Settings 1
 - If all videos have identical lighting conditions and frame rate, one detection entry can be used for all; name it “Detection for all”
 - OR if there are 2 lighting conditions or 2 different frame rates, create detection setting entries for each condition and apply as appropriate on the trial list
 - OR if each video has different lighting, rename it to the animal ID number for each trial
 - Caution: you cannot edit detection settings that are applied to other acquired trials. If one, or a few trials need detection alterations, create new detection entries for them.
 - Detection settings can also be done using automated set-up without issue
 - To use this method, trace a box around the mouse for each trial, and rename each setting with the animal ID number
 - Click Save to save the file

Repeat for all other animals:

- Click on previous animal ID under Arena Settings: right-click → duplicate → name as next animal ID → click Grab Background Image Button in bottom right → find video → Grab → delete and redraw or adjust rulers as needed → adjust Arenas and center boxes → click Validate Setup
- Click on previous animal ID under Trial Control Settings: right-click → duplicate and name with next animal ID → adjust the delay time in the “Start” box for that mouse’s video
- *Only if using multiple detection settings*: Click on previous Animal ID under Detection Settings: right-click → duplicate and name with next animal ID → automated set-up → outline the mouse in each video

Trial List

- Trial List → Add Trials → # of Animals → Ok
- Add Variable → rename animal ID#
- Add Videos → Alphabetical → Browse → select all videos and import them in order from same folder
- Make list in numerical order of animal ID#s → copy and paste into blank columns →
 - Each row should have the same animal ID#s all across

Acquisition

- Acquisition → Acquisition → Track All Planned → Ready for Start (red circle button) → videos are analyzed
- Track editor → if using 3 body points, then check if trials need arrow swaps; refer to arrow swap protocol

Analysis

- Click Analysis Profile 1
 - Under Location → click the box next to “In zone” → select S5 (only)
 - Trial Statistics tab: Frequency + Cumulative Duration + Latency to First + Cumulative Duration (%)
 - Add → right click “In zone” and rename to “Center”
- Results → Statistics and Charts → Calculate → Export Data